

EFFECT OF PROCESSING CONDITIONS ON THE QUALITY OF OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE LAMINATES MADE BY AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Over the years, out-of-autoclave(OOA) processing has become an integral part of composites technologies, which uses conventional oven and atmospheric pressure to make structural components at comparatively lower price. Meanwhile, Automated Fiber Placement(AFP) technology brings to manufacturing fast rate of material deposition repeatability and consistency, also allows for complex geometries, which traditional layups cannot match. Therefore, the combination of AFP and OOA technology can not only increase manufacturing rate but also help deliver parts of superior quality. However, reducing the voids content and controlling the quality of parts give challenges to the manufacturing.

In this paper, the effects of processing parameters on the quality of OOA composites manufactured by AFP have been investigated, including lay-up rate and compaction force. Porosity in the parts was determined by optical microscopy and image analysis. From the comparisons of voids content in the parts, lower lay-up rate and higher compaction force can help to reduce voids. The slight gaps and overlaps induced by AFP processing between each tow and their effects on the variation through thickness have also been identified. The optimum parameters in CYCOM5320-1/IM7 composites manufactured by AFP are 1.5 in./s laying-up speed, 40lb compaction force and 100°C nozzle temperature. In addition, the AFP samples have better results on 0° tensile and in-plane shear tests, when compared with HLU samples, while the 0° compressive properties need to be retested using thicker coupons.

1 INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, thermoset composites have been hand laid-up and cured in an autoclave. Over the years, OOA processing has become an integral part of composites technologies, since it allow fast prototyping and manufacturing flexibility, which is cheaper than autoclave processing. Currently, many researchers have attempted to achieve high quality OOA composite parts for aerospace primary structures applications [1-3].

However, to further reduce the cost of OOA composite parts, it is necessary to combine automated composite manufacturing and OOA technology together, which can not only increase manufacturing rate but also help deliver parts of superior quality. One of the fastest evolving automated composite manufacturing technology is automated fiber placement (AFP), where impregnated fiber tows are mechanically and automatically placed on a tool to build a complex composite laminate, while multiple tows can be applied together to increase the manufacturing rate[4,5]. However, reducing the

voids content and controlling the quality of parts give challenges to the OOA composites manufactured by AFP processing.

In this paper, the effects of processing parameters on the quality of OOA composites manufactured by AFP have been investigated, including lay-up rate, compaction force and applied temperature. Porosity in the parts was determined by optical microscopy and image analysis. Mechanical properties of OOA laminates made by both AFP and Hand Lay-up (HLU) processing were tested to evaluate the quality.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Materials

The prepregs studied were all uni-directional, which were summarized in Table 1. Materials used for edge breathing were 4in. width plain weave fiberglass fabric. Materials used for bagging were all from Airtech, including non-perforated release film, breather cloth, bagging film and sealant tape.

Processing	AFP	HLU
Name	CYCOM 5320-1FI /IM7	CYCOM 5320-1/IM7
Fiber Area Weight	145 gsm	145 gsm
Resin Content	33% weight content	33% weight content
Width	0.25 in.	5.98 in.
Description	Fully impregnated	Partially impregnated, with dry fiber channels in the center

Table 1: Summary of prepregs used in the experiments.

2.2 AFP processing

The AFP machine from Automated Dynamics Corporation (ADC) has been used to manufacture the samples with 0.25in. width prepregs. This machine uses a Kawasaki robotic arm for the axial movement and can work in a cylindrical envelope of 10 feet in length by 6 feet in diameter. The thermoset head can support up to 4 prepreg tows at the same time. The process parameters investigated in AFP processing are lay-up rate, compaction force and applied temperature.

2.3 HLU processing

For samples made by HLU processing, the prepregs were laid on flat mold using a roller to remove entrapped air. After laying down each two layers, the entire lay-up was enclosed in a vacuum bag and debulked for 15-20min under 29.7in. Hg vacuum pressure.

2.4 Bagging procedure

Figure 1 shows the bagging procedure for CYCOM 5320-1/IM7, recommended by Cytec Company [6].

Figure 1: Bagging procedure recommended by Cytec Company.

2.5 Curing procedure

Table 2 shows the two cure cycles for CYCOM 5320-1/IM7, recommended by Cytec Company [6]. The cure cycle B was chosen to be used in the paper.

Parameter	Cure Cycle A	Cure Cycle B
Ramp Rate	0.6-1.7°C/min	0.6-2.8°C/min
Cure Temperature	93 ± 6°C	121 ± 6°C
Cure Time	12 hrs	3 hrs
Free-Standing Post Cure	2hrs at 177°C	2 hrs at 177°C

Table 2: Two cure cycles for for CYCOM 5320-1/IM7

2.6 Microscopic observation

Optical microscopy was performed on the middle of samples made by various manufacturing methods to determine the quality of the laminate by determination of voids areas. The coupons were polished on a MECATECH 234 polishing machine, scanned using Fein Optic microscope with a magnification of 5×.

2.7 Mechanical tests

Mechanical tests to determine the 0° tensile, 0° compressive and in-plane shear properties were performed on coupons made by both AFP and HLU processing, comparing with datasheet from Cytec Company [6]. The testing machine used was 250kN MTS machine.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Processing parameters for OOA composites made by AFP

Figure 2 shows the 12in. ×12in., [0/45/90/-45]_{2S} laminates made by AFP processing, with 3.0 in./s laying-up speed, 30lb compaction force and 100°C nozzle temperature. From this picture it is clear that there are some gaps in the laminate. Figure 3 shows microscopic images of the middle of the laminates. The important observation was there are many voids in the gaps and interlayer areas, while no major voids were observed in the overlaps area. So it is suggested to make no gaps laminates, to achieve that, we need to lay-up just one tow for each time.

Figure 2: Laminates with gaps inside made by AFP processing

Table 3 summaries the defects induced in AFP processing when manufacturing OOA composites and their solutions.

Figure 4 shows the microscopic images of the coupons made by AFP using different parameters. It is evident that the samples made by using 1.5 in./s laying-up speed, 40lb compaction force and 100°C nozzle temperature have better quality, with no significant voids in the laminate.

Figure 3: Microscopic images of the coupons cut from the middle of the laminates with gaps (5× magnification)

Defects		Solutions
Gaps between tows		Lay down one tow for each time
Resin rich area		
Voids	In gaps area	Slowing the lay down speed Increasing compaction force
	Between layers	
Interlaminar bonding		Increasing compaction force Adjusting heating temperature
Flat surface		No gaps Less overlaps

Table 3: Summary of the defects induced in AFP processing and their solutions

Figure 4: Microscopic images of the coupons made by AFP using different parameters (with magnification of 5×): (a) 1.0in./s laying-up speed, 30lb compaction force and 100°C nozzle temperature; (b) 1.5 in./s laying-up speed, 40lb compaction force and 100°C nozzle temperature; (c) 1.5 in./s laying-up speed, 30lb compaction force and 130°C nozzle temperature.

Figure 5 shows the images of void-free laminates made by AFP with different stacking sequence $[45/-45]_{2S}$ and $[0]_8$, respectively.

Figure 5: Images of void-free laminates made by AFP processing: (a) Stacking sequence $[45/-45]_{2s}$; (b) Stacking sequence $[0]_8$. (Magnification $5\times$ for microscopic images)

3.2 Mechanical Tests

0° tensile, 0° compressive and in-plane shear properties of both AFP and HLU laminates were tested and compared with the datasheet, according to ASTM D3039, ASTM D3410 and ASTM D3518, respectively[7-9]. The stacking sequence for each tests were $[0]_8$, $[0]_8$, $[45/-45]_{4s}$. Figure 6 summaries the results. For tensile and shear strength, the samples made by AFP produced better results than that made by HLU, while they have almost the same modulus. However, the 0° compressive results shows significant lower results than datasheet, which may be caused by insufficient layers, since the coupons only have 8 layers.

(a) 0° tensile properties

(b) 0° compressive properties

(c) In-plane shear properties

Figure 6: Summary of the mechanical results for both AFP and HLU samples.

4 CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that high quality of laminates made by AFP process depends on the processing parameters fed to the AFP system. Moreover, the compaction force applied during the AFP lay-up process plays an important role, which helps to produce void-free laminate. The optimum parameters in CYCOM5320-1/IM7 composites manufactured by AFP are 1.5 in./s laying-up speed, 40lb compaction force and 100°C nozzle temperature. In addition, the AFP samples have better results on 0° tensile and in-plane shear tests, when compared with HLU samples, while the 0° compressive properties need to be retested using thicker coupons.

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